

ANALYSIS OF THE BEEF VALUE CHAIN IN KOGI STATE, NIGERIA

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Article History

Received on: 25 Jul- 2023

Revised on: 26-Sep-2023

Accepted on: 26 Oct-2023

First Published:30-Dec-2023

Cite this Article as

Ohiemi, S.I., Ibrahim M.K., Adejo, P.E. Yusuf, S.O. and Valentine, E.O. (2023), "Analysis Of The Beef Value Chain In Kogi State, Nigeria", *International Journal of Marketing & Financial Management*, Volume 11, Issue 2, 2023, pp 58-80. DOI : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10900164>

Keywords: Value chain, Actors, Value addition, Beef

Paper Type: Research Article

ABSTRACT

Aim of the Study: *The study attempts to answer the question; What are the activities of the beef value chain actors?*

Design/Methodology: *Primary data were used to explore the aim of the study through descriptive statistics, gross margin analysis, participatory analysis and factor analysis.*

Findings: *Results showed that the majority of respondents were married and migrants. The majority of the actors in the value chain employed unskilled labour and did not employ women. The marketers made a reasonable amount of profit over the producers and processors. The findings show that male-headed households dominate the beef production industry.*

Practical implications: *This study shows that constraints faced by the producers, marketers and processors revealed that factors loaded on factor 1 such as fake drugs, drought, Far Distances to Drug Centres, invasion of wild animals, inadequate dipping system, high capital, high cost of drugs respectively, were the major constraints faced by actors in the value chain.*

Originality/value: *The activities of producers, processors and marketers along the beef value chain were evaluated. A major recommendation after this study is that the government should construct and establish*

a feeling system at strategic places. The banks and microfinance industries should implement unique credit and guarantee programs, and legislators must provide easily available information systems.

1. INTRODUCTION

A significant agricultural product in the global economy is beef. An annual production of 65 million tons of beef is produced worldwide using 300 million head of cattle. (FAO, 2017). The United States is the world's biggest producer of beef producing nearly 20%, followed by Brazil (15%) and the European Union (13%) (FAS/USDA, 2017). Globally, less than 5% of beef is exported on average. Trade policies are primarily concerned with spoiling and possible cold chain collapse due to the high weight of beef. (FAO, 2017).

By 2050, it is anticipated that meat consumption in Africa will rise to 34.8 million tons, with an annual growth rate of around 2.8%. By 2050, there will be an 8.9 million tons rise in the consumption of beef alone (LSDIA, 2014). About 14 countries including Nigeria engage in importing tonnes of beef. These countries include Burundi; (1,212tonnes), Guinea (874 tonnes), Gabon (522tonnes), Liberia (189tonnes), Sudan (105 tonnes), Algeria (87 tonnes), Chad (14 tonnes), Burkina Faso (7 tonnes) and Libya (17 tonnes) (FAO, 2016).

Nigeria's greatest market is the cattle trade, with live animals moving from the country's northern regions to its southernmost regions to be sold to end consumers (Aboah *et al.*, 2021). These import data show that beef is a widely traded item, and there may be a lot of room for growth in the trade of beef, particularly in developing nations like Nigeria. The popularity of eating beef and Nigerian customers consider cattle to be a valuable livestock in the country (Gambo 2020). According to Grain Diesel (2010), Nigeria is the primary producer of West and Central African beef cattle. Estimates place Nigeria's cow herds at about 16 million, greatly exceeding those of Niger. Despite of its leading role in production, Nigeria still imports about 835 tonnes of beef in the foreign trade market (FAO, 2016). There are 19.5 million heads of livestock in Nigeria with the production of about 380,000 metric tons of meat per year.

In addition to making a significant contribution to GDP, the Nigerian beef cattle business also significantly boosts the country's supply of animal protein. (Tewe, 2010). The cattle value chain receives the most contribution from this business. (Kosgey *et al.*, 2011, Otieno *et al.*, 2012). It is also a significant source of income and jobs (Alarcon *et al.*, 2017). Millions of Nigerians who live in families that raise livestock and those who work in the beef value chain within the country's sub-dry and sub-arid ecological divisions rely on the industry for their subsistence. (FAO, 2006; Umar *et al.*, 2008). Nigeria has a variety of animal protein sources, but recent research indicates that cow products are the most popular and widely consumed. (Tibi and Aphunu, 2010).

The activities of numerous actors, ranging from production to marketing, are part of the beef value chain. It is challenging to pinpoint the precise number of agents throughout the value

chain. The buyer's many unfixed fees and commissions, which vary based on his bargaining position, further complicate this (Olukosi *et al.*, 2007). According to studies, an ineffective distribution system is produced when there are an excessive number of intermediaries inside the selling various items derived from and by animals (Emokaro and Amadasun, 2012).

Development practitioners and developing nations have employed numerous value chain methodologies to investigate the interplay of heterogeneous entities engaged in every phase of the production, processing, and marketing channel (Guilani *et al.*, 2005). The method evaluates how a series of actions taken by actors backed by different business service providers and impacted by the specific business environment in which they operate create value in an end market. It also looks at the structure of vertical relationships between buyers and sellers. (BAVCP, 2012).

Therefore, it is necessary to examine the actions of those involved in Kogi State, Nigeria's cattle value chain. The study's precise objectives are to:

- characterize the main actors' socio demographic traits;
- determine the main participants in the value chain and create a map of their operations;
- identify the various potential employment opportunities in the value chain;
- determine the value chain's shared production, processing, and marketing strategies;
- determine the profitability level of major enterprises in the value chain;
- determine the principal limitations encountered in the value chain

2. METHODOLOGY

The Kogi State, the study area, is situated in Nigeria's central area, or Middle Belt. Because of the confluence of the Rivers At their capital, Lokoja, Niger and Benue established the first administrative center of Nigeria today—it is also known as the Confluence State. The only state in Nigeria that borders ten other states is Kogi State.

The land region is located between latitude 7.500°N6.700°E and longitude 7°30'N 6°42'E. Additionally, the land area measures 29,833 km² (11,519 sq mi). Along when fishing in places near rivers, such as Lokoja, Idah, IBaji, and Bassa, the state's economy primarily depends on agriculture. Steel, coal, oil, and other minerals reserves are also present in the state. Parts of Kwara State and Benue State were combined to create the state in 1991. Igala, Ebira, and Okun are the three primary Kogi's ethnic groupings and languages; further groups include Bassa-Nge, Gwari, Kakanda, Oworo people, Ogori, Magongo, and Idoma.

The Nigeria Bureau of Statistics (2016) provided a population prediction that is currently projected at 4,473,500. The foundation of the economy is agriculture. The state produces a wide variety of agricultural products, including melon, cashews, groundnuts, maize, cassava, yam, and palm oil. Tin, iron, limestone, and coal, and Mineral resources include, for instance, petroleum. Ajaokuta Steel Company Limited, Nigeria's biggest steel and iron factory, and Obajana Cement Factory, one of the biggest cement manufacturers in Africa, are both located in the state.

To choose respondents for this study, a combination of purposive and random selection techniques were employed. In the selection of the producers, two blocks with pastoralists/ herds settlements were purposively selected from across the four agricultural Zones (A, B, C & D). In this case, Kabbaand Aiyetoro blocks from zone A, Ankpa and Dekina blocks from Zone B, Lokoja and KotoKarfe blocks from Zone C, Okpo and Itobe blocks from Zone D. This was followed by the random selection of ten (10) producers from the identified settlements in each of the blocks. In all 80 cattle producers were interviewed for this study.

In the case of the processors and marketers, a block was purposively selected from every farming zone according to having a standard abattoir/meat slab. The blocks proposed to be selected are Kabba block from zone A, Ankpa block from zone B, Lokoja block from zone C and Ejule block from zone D. This was followed by a random selection of 15 processors and marketers. A list of the registered processors and Marketers were obtained from relevant associations which are the Butchers Association, Mayeti Allah who are Fulani cattle rearers, Association of marketers. A total of sixty (60) processors and 60 marketers were selected. In all, 200 Respondents were chosen and interviewed for this study. A combination of descriptive statistics, participatory value chain analysis, gross margin analysis and factor analysis.

With the aid of participatory value chain analysis and descriptive statistics like frequency, percentage, mean, and mode, Objectives 1, 2, 3, and 4 were examined.

Objective 5 was evaluated using gross margin analysis.

Using the factor analysis, objective 6 was examined.

Model Specification

Gross Margin

$GM = TR - TVC$

Where

GM = Gross Margin

TR = Total Revenue

TVC = Total Variable Cost

2.1 Participatory Value Chain Analysis

One technique for mapping the value chain that involves all of the important informants and stakeholders is Participatory Value Chain Analysis (PVCA). PVCA, in its most basic form, is gathering stakeholders who are knowledgeable about various chain levels to create a common flow map. (Mayoux, 2003).

2.2 Factor Analysis

Using a potentially smaller number of factors, or invisible variables, factor analysis is An analysis of statistics technique used to characterize differences between the observed, associated variables. In reaction to latent variables that are not observed, factor analysis looks for such joint variations. The potential factors are treated as linear combinations of the observable variables

plus "error" terms. The purpose of factor analysis is to identify independent latent variables.

$$x_j = a_{j1}f_1 + a_{j2}f_2 + \dots + a_{jm}f_m + e_j$$

Where $e_j = 1, 2, \dots, p$

P stands for the number of variables in the traditional factor analysis mathematical model. (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_p) and m indicates how many underlying elements there are (f_1, f_2, \dots, f_m). x_j is the variable that the latent factors reflect.

3. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

The collected data were analyzed and the results are presented here.

3.1 Socio-Demographic Characteristics of Beef Cattle Respondents

Table 1's results for socio demographic factors indicate that, on average, 97.5 % of pastoralist family heads were men, and just 2.5 % were women. The result also shows that all the marketers interviewed were male (100%). As for the processors, majority of them were male (60%), however significant proportion of them were female (40%). This suggests that men are more involved in the value chain of beef cattle than women, which is understandable given the demanding labour and ensuing stress associated with the production, marketing, and processing of beef cattle. The average age was observed to be 56 years. This implies that respondents are within the active working age range. with years of experience below 20 years to be (29.2%) and majority with years of experience between 20-60 years (71.6%). As for marketers, years of experience below 20 years (56.8%) are majority. That of processors (78.4%) is majority below 20 years. This suggests that for the producers, the higher the years of expertise, the greater the outcome and from the result majority is supposed to be proficient in the abilities needed for top performance. About 70% of the pastoralist had no formal education. The result of marketers shows that only 3.3% had no formal education and 46.7% have attained secondary education. As for the processors, 21.7% had no formal education whereas, 36.7% attained primary education. This suggests that the bulk of the producers have not attended school; this could be because of their adherence to customs, religions, or cultures. Household size was within the age range of 10 – 15 members. majority of beef cattle actors were married (61.7%). This indicates that married people have a social responsibility to take care of their households, and the bulk of them are, predictably, migrants. (75%).

Table 1: The Actor Distribution Based on Sociodemographic Factors

Socio-demographic indicators	Producers		Marketers		Processors	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Gender						
Male	78	97.5	60	100	36	60
Female	2	2.5	0	0	24	40
Total	80	100	60	100	60	100
Age						

1-30	8	10.1	7	11.7	21	34.9
31-40	29	36.5	22	36.7	27	45
41-50	25	31.5	22	36.7	11	18.3
51-60	10	12.7	8	13.3	1	1.7
61-70	6	7.7	1	1.7	0	0
71-80	2	2.6	0	0	0	0
Total	80	100	60	100	60	100
Experience						
1-20	23	29.2	34	56.8	47	78.4
21-30	38	47.7	20	33.4	12	20
31-40	14	17.5	5	8.4	1	1.7
41-50	4	5.1	1	1.7	0	0
51-60	1	1.3	0	0	0	0
Total	80	100	60	100	60	100
Edu. Status						
No formal	56	70	2	3.3	13	21.7
Primary	17	21.3	17	28.3	12	36.7
Secondary	3	3.8	28	48.7	18	30
Tertiary	4	5	13	21.7	7	11.7
Total	80	100	60	100	60	100
HHS						
1-10	28	35.2			55	91.1
10-15	37	46.4			5	8.4
16-20	14	17.6			0	0
21-25	1	1.3			0	0
Total	80	100			60	100
Marital status						
Single					17	28.3
Married					37	61.7
Widowed					6	10
Total					60	100
Origin						
Native	20	25				
Migrant	60	75				
Total	80	100				

Source: Field survey, 2019.

4. Mapping of Beef Cattle Value Chain

4.1 Producer

The majority of producers 81.3% agreed that channel two best summed up their marketing and production efforts. The channels depict an interaction where farmers have personal service providers take care of their beef cattle and/or purchase medications or other inputs directly. When the cattle reach maturity, producers might choose to sell to wholesalers, brokers/traders, or end users directly. This suggests that producers are presented with a multitude of marketing options. **Marketers**

According to Table 2, the majority of marketers (70%) felt that channels one and three provided the greatest description of their marketing efforts. According to the channels, marketers purchase beef calves at the farm gate and then resell to retailers, hotels, and restaurants, as well as directly to customers. This suggests that the beef cattle travel through intermediaries between the producer and the end users in either case.

4.2 Processors

Furthermore, Table 2 showed that the majority of processors (46.7%) thought that channel three best reflected their processing activities. The channel provides a clear link in which smaller processors buy from larger processors, such as butchers and abattoirs, add value (i.e., process further) and sell straight to end users. This suggests that processors purchase beef animals from market-based butchers and abattoirs, process the meat (i.e., add value), and then sell it to customers.

Table 2: Channels Describing Activities of Actors in the Value Chain

Actors	Channel	Frequency	Percentage
Producer	Channel one	7	8.8
	Channel two	65	81.3
	Channel three	8	10
Total		80	100
Marketer	Channel one	21	35
	Channel two	18	30
	Channel three	21	35
Total		60	100
Processor	Channel one	14	23.3
	Channel two	18	30
	Channel three	28	46.7
Total		60	100

Source: Field survey, 2019.

4.3 Tracking Potential Employment Opportunities in the Beef Value Chain

Table 3 makes clear that the majority of producers (60%) use hired labour to complete their tasks. This suggests that raising beef cattle involves labour-intensive, time-consuming tasks that call for more workers. As a result, there is a chance that young people may participate actively in the industrial processes. The majority of the labour used is in herding (59.2%). According to the results, the majority of producers will use labour for 51–60 hours each week. They would need 55.5 hours of labour per week on average, primarily for herding duties. This equates to 222 hours every month. (98.8%) perform manual labour. This suggests that since production activities need unskilled labour, young people without jobs can readily fit in. The bulk of employers—92.5%—do not employ women, according to the findings. This suggests that because production tasks are stressful, men are more involved in the raising of beef cattle. The outcome reveals that 98.8% of

employers use women for cleaning jobs. On the other hand, (1.3%) hire female veterinarians. This suggests that women are solely used as veterinary agents and as cleaners to remove cow excrement.

Table 3: Presence of Employment Opportunities at Production Stage

Indicators	Frequency	Percentage
Engagement of paid labour		
Yes	48	60
No	32	40
Total	80	100
Operation Segment		
Herding	31	59.2
Cleaning	3	3.6
Slaughtering	6	12.7
Herder, cleaner	8	24.5
Total	48	100
Hours of labour required (weekly)		
1-50	6	12.6
51-60	35	57.6
61-70	7	30.1
Total	48	100
Skills Requirement		
Skilled	1	1.3
Unskilled	47	98.8
Total	48	100
Opportunities for Women		
Yes	6	7.5
No	42	92.5
Total	48	100
Areas of Engaging women		
Cleaner	31	98.8
Vet doctor	1	1.3
Total	32	100

Source: Field survey 2019

5. MARKETERS

The findings indicate that 56.7% of labour is needed for marketers, which is the majority. This suggests that marketing activities take labour seriously because they require a lot of time, labour-intensive logistics (transporting, loading, unloading, etc.), and market research. The young

people without jobs can therefore continue to be actively involved. According to the statistics, 43.3 percent mostly engages in slaughtering operations. Additionally, the results showed that the majority of labour 98.3% is unskilled in marketing. The results indicated that 98.3% of them do not hire women predominately. However, only about 8.3% employ women. This implies that marketing activities do not suit women. As earlier said, marketing of beef cattle involves rigorous stress whose nature is tedious. About 91.7% of women are not employed in marketing beef cattle. However, 6.7% and 1.7% are employed as veterinary doctors and informants respectively. This implies that women are only employed when information is required about beef cattle marketing especially from buyers and also when veterinary services are needed.

Table 3.1 Employment opportunities in marketing activities

Indicators	Frequency	Percentage
Engagement of Paid Labour		
Yes	34	56.7
No	26	43.3
Total	60	100
Operation Segment		
Slaughtering	26	43.3
Cleaning, informant	3	21.3
Transporter, loader/unloader	5	38.3
Total	34	100
Skill Requirement		
Skilled	1	1.7
Unskilled	33	98.3
Total	34	100
Opportunities for Women		
Yes	5	8.3
No	29	98.3
Total	34	100
Areas of engaging women		
None employ	55	91.7
Veterinary agent	4	6.7
Informant	1	1.7
Total	60	100

Source: Field survey, 2019.

5.1 Processors

Result from Table 3.3.3 had shown that 63.3% of processors which is majority do not employ labour. However, 36.7% employ labour. This implies that beef processing activities is not as hectic as that of production and marketing. Hence, requires less labour. 56.7% requires labour in

slaughtering aspect, only a small proportion (3.3%) requires labour in 10% in roasting, sticking, spicing aspects. This implies that activities where labour is required in processing includes slaughtering, cutting, frying, boiling, roasting, sticking, spicing. Majority (56.7%) requires 10-20 hours of labour per week. This implies that processing activities do not take much time to be carried out. On average 15 hours of labour is required per week. This will translate to 60 hour of labour in a month. This finding revealed that majority (98.3%) required unskilled labour while 1.7% are skilled. This implies that processing activities are not learnt in a formal setting. It could be that the activities are being mastered via constant practice over time. (68.3%) employ women in processing. However, (31.7%) do not employ women. This implies that women participate actively in processing activities since it does not require rigorous work. Also, the results showed that women majorly (35%) employ women in frying, cooking and spicing aspect. Only a small proportion (3.3%) engaged in spicing aspect. This implies that women are more employed in the aspect of frying, cooking and spicing. This could be very possible as majority of women are involved in hotels and restaurant business. From the findings of identifying various employment opportunities for producers, marketers and processors in the value chain, it had been revealed that producers employ more labour.

Table 3.2 Employment opportunities in Processing Activities

Indicators	Frequency	Percentage
Engagement of Paid Labour		
Yes	22	36.7
No	38	63.3
Total	60	100
Operation Segment		
Slaughtering	10	56.7
Cutting, frying, boiling aspects	6	20.7
Roasting, spicing, sticking aspects	2	3.3
Saucing, boiling	1	1.7
Sticking, spicing	3	18.5
Total	22	100
Hours of Labour Required (Weekly)		
1-10	3	18.5
10-20	10	56.7
21-30	7	21.5
31-40	2	3.3
Total	22	100
Skill Requirement		
Skilled	1	1.7
Unskilled	21	98.3

Total	22	100
Opportunities for Women		
Yes	12	68.3
No	10	31.7
Total	22	100
Areas of Engaging Women		
None employ women	19	31.7
Frying, cooking, spicing	21	35
Boiling, frying, saucing	9	15
Spicing	2	3.3
Frying, re-cutting	4	6.7
Roasting, spicing	5	8.3
Total	60	100

Source: Field survey, 2019

5.2 Features of Beef Value Chain Production, Processing, and Marketing

82.5% of producers used an extensive system of cattle rearing, according to the results of the production system in the beef value chain, as shown in Table 4.1. Nevertheless, 13.5% employed a semi-intense system and 3.8% an intensive system. This suggests that the vast majority of producers used a conventional or extended approach. This might be well-liked since it lowers production expenses, such as feed costs. 88.8% of people use the open housing scheme. The white Fulani breed was found to be stocked by the majority of producers (41.3%). This could be traced to the fact that white Fulani breed has the capacity to fend off illnesses and flourish in a range of harsh condition. This discovery can be found in line with (Alphonsus *et al.*,2012) who made the report white Fulani provided much of the beef consumed throughout Nigeria. The result revealed that majority (73.8%) of producers uses improved technology. This indicates that the majority of pastoralists utilize various forms of advanced technology and are aware of it. This may be attributed to their increased usage of contemporary restraint systems, veterinary services, artificial insemination, identification, and dipping systems.

Table 4.1: Respondent distribution based on characteristics related to productivity Indicators		
	Frequency	Percentage
Production System		
Intensive	3	3.8
Extensive	66	82.5
Semi-intensive	11	13.5
Total	80	100
Housing System		
Open housing system	71	88.8
Fixed housing system	9	11.3

Total	80	100
Cattle Breed		
Kazana, white Fulani, bokolo (mix)	15	18.8
White Fulani	33	41.3
Bunaji, white Fulani (mix)	10	12.5
Bokolo	12	15
Bunaji	10	12.5
Total	80	100
Technology Use		
Yes	59	73.8
No	21	26.3
Total	80	100
Source: Field survey, 2019		

6. MARKETERS

The findings indicate that middlemen make up 46.7% of marketers. But 10% are retailers and a sizeable number (43.3%) are wholesalers. This suggests that intermediaries who serve as a link between buyers and pastoralists control most of the cattle that are beef marketing in the research region. Findings revealed that majority (46.7%) sold beef cattle to tertiary/terminal market. This implies that before marketing the cattle, there exist a long distribution process and activities to different categories of marketers before it gets to the end users. Majority 73.3% of marketers sold their beef cattle via cash. Also the result shows that 45% of marketers agree that average distance from point of production to the market is less than 20km. This implies that the average distance from point of purchase to where cattle are assembled is not farther than 20km and majority attest to this fact. And the reason could be that most of the pastoralists reside in the outskirts of the marketer's resident. This reduces marketing costs for the marketers. The findings revealed that 66.7% of the marketers had access to credit. This implies that most of the marketers had access to credit and the reason could be due to the fact that they are members of at least one or two co-operatives. Findings had shown that 46.7% of marketers got credit from savings and credit group. This implies that a large number of marketers rely on informal source of getting credit/loan (savings and credit group). The findings in this study are in agreement with those published by Mafimisebi *et al* (2013) in southern Nigeria.

Table 4.2: Distribution of traits linked to marketing throughout the value chain for beef

Indicators	Frequency	Percentage
Skill of Operation		
Wholesaler	26	43.3
Retailer	6	10
Middlemen	28	46.7

Total	60	100
Market Type		
Bush market	1	1.7
Primary market	7	11.7
Secondary market	24	40.8
Tertiary/terminal market	28	46.7
Total	60	100
Mode of Transaction		
By cash	44	73.3
By credit	1	1.7
Both	15	25
Total	60	100
Distance to Market		
1-20	27	45
21-30	23	38.3
31-40	0	0
41-50	10	16.7
Total	60	100
Access to credit		
Yes	40	66.7
No	20	33.3
Total	60	100
Credit source		
Savings and credit group	28	46.7
Micro finance institution	2	14.5
Cooperatives/contribution	10	39.5
Total	40	100
Source: Field survey, 2019		

6.1 Processors

It has been revealed from Table 4.3 that 56.7% processors carry out activities on small scale level. Although (26.7%) at medium scale and (16.7%) at large scale. This suggests that small-scale processing is what the majority of processors in the research area do. The activities include those working in hotels, restaurants, barbeque sellers etc. Reason could also be that most consumers have easy access to beef cuts in the study area and easily prepares them by themselves for consumption. 41.7% processors identify that frying, spicing, boiling are the common and major activities carried out by the processors. Although 26.7% identify roasting, sticking, spicing, 11.7% identify cutting, grading, roasting, 13.4% identify cutting, roasting, refrigerating, grading. This implies that processors in the value chain actually engage in numerous processing activities but with frying, spicing and boiling as majority. Improved

technology was used by processors in the value chain as presented in Table 4.4.3 shows that 60% processors make use of improved technology while 40% do not. This implies that most processors are aware of the use of improved technology. The technology that are used in the study area could include gas cooker, deep fryer, use of iron rod stoves, use of packaging sticks, use of powdered seasonings e.tc. Findings show that 80% of processors have direct contact with consumers. With, only 1.7% having indirect contact.18.3% engage in both. This implies that processors prefer dealing directly with their consumers. It could be as a result of meeting their consumers taste and building a friendly relationship with them in other to ensure continuity of business. Majority (55%) processors do not have access to credit. About 45% have access to different forms of credit. Lack of collateral to secure a loan, ignorance on how to secure one, and difficult loan application processes could be the cause of credit absence. Also, since their scale of processing is small scale, it would be difficult for them to get access to credit. However, 1.7% gets from commercial banks, 28.3% from savings and credit group,8.3% from contribution group and 6.7% from cooperatives. This implies that they majorly finance their business from their personal savings. 68.3% processors do not undergo training. While only 31.7% undergo training. This implies that majority of the processors do not undergo any training process. It could be that through consistency and watching of their predecessors they tend to learn the processing activities and skills.

Table 4.3:Distribution of Processing-Related Features in the Value Chain for Beef		
Indicators	Scale of Operation	Frequency
Percentage		
Small scale	34	56.7
Large scale	10	16.7
Medium	16	26.7
Total	60	100
Processing activities		
Roasting, sticking, spicing	16	26.7
Frying,spicing,boiling	25	41.7
Recutting,frying,boiling	4	6.7
Cutting, roasting,refrigerating,grading	8	13.4
Cutting,grading,roasting	7	11.7
Total	60	100
Technology Adoption		
Yes	36	60
No	24	40
Total	60	100
Consumers Contact		
Direct	48	80
Indirect	1	1.7

Both	11	18.3
Total	60	100
Access to credit		
Yes	27	45
No	33	55
Total	60	100
Credit Source		
None collects credit	33	55
Savings and credit group	17	28.3
Commercial banks	1	1.7
Contribution group	5	8.3
Cooperatives	4	6.7
Total	60	100
Participation in Training		
Yes	19	31.7
No	41	68.3
Total	60	100

Source: Field survey,2019.

6.2 Profitability of Beef Value Chain Production, Processing, and Marketing Businesses

In this part, the findings from the examination of the profitability of businesses involved in the production, processing, and marketing of beef are given. Based on an analysis of gross margin for each of the three businesses, an estimate of net profit was given. Gross margin, net profit income in both percentage and naira, total revenue, and total variable costs are among the variables taken into account in this study.

The projection from the results revealed that the production, processing and marketing enterprises are profitable. With the producer having a gross margin of ₦79,394.00 and a net profit of 55%, the marketer had a gross margin of ₦84,500.33 and net profit of 28%, the processor also had a gross margin of ₦5,691.3 and net profit of 38%. This implies that for an individual going into beef cattle production, processing and marketing should expect a positive return. The findings revealed that the gross margin of marketers (₦84,500.33) is higher compared to the gross margin of producers (₦79,394) and that of processors (₦5,691.3). This implies that marketers in the beef cattle value chain makes more profit than producers and processors. This could be traced back to the role of middlemen (marketers) in any business venture where they are served to over exploit the buyers and add more value to a commodity making them to sell at a higher price than the producers of that commodity. This result agree with the report of (Mafimisebi, 2011), upon reporting that cattle marketing yields profits for several marketing categories. In order to affect their final sale price in the terminal market, the marketers may also incorporate various additional costs incurred.

Unequivocally, from the results, it is evident that the beef cattle business for the different categories of actors says producer, marketer and processor were profitable.

Table 5.1: Analysis of Production Enterprise in the Beef Value Chain

Cost incurred per unit of beef cattle	TVC (₦)
Day old calf	24,000
Labour cost	5,000.00
Drugs/medication	5,000.00
Dipping/spraying	5,000.00
Transportation cost	10,000.00
Movement permit	8,668.50
Veterinary services	4,000.00
Feed cost	3,000.00
Total	65,668.5
Total Revenue	
Cattle selling price	145,062.50
Gross Margin (TR-TVC)	79,394.00
NPI (GM/TRx100)	55%
Source: Field survey,2019	

Table 5.2 : Analysis of Marketing Enterprise in the Beef Value Chain

Cost incurred per unit of beef cattle	TVC (₦)
Purchasing price of matured cattle	162,500.00
Market dues	2,000.00
Movement permit	6,000.00
Transportation cost	15,000.00
Loss of cattle	20,000.00
Labour cost	1,000.00
Communication cost	1,000.00
Loading/unloading	1,000.00
Cold-room fee	2,500.00
Feed/fattening cost	5,000.00
Total	216,000.00
Total Revenue	
Cattle selling price	300,500.33
Gross Margin (TR-TVC)	84,500.33
NPI (GM/TRx100)	28%

Source: Field survey, 2019

Table 5.3 : Analysis of Processing Enterprise in the Beef Value Chain

Cost incurred for 5kg of beef	Number of beef cuts	Beef cuts/ ₦	TVC (₦)
Purchasing price			6,750.00
Transportation cost			200.00
Storage/preservation cost			150.50
Market dues			500.00
Firewood cost			250.00
Vegetable oil/onions			1,158.20
Seasoning cost			300.00
Total			9,308.7
Total Revenue			
Selling price after processing	100	150	15,000.00
Gross Margin (TR-TVC)			5691.3
NPI (GM/TRx100)			38%

Source: Field survey, 2019

$$\text{Gross margin} = \text{TR} - \text{TVC}$$

$$\text{Net profit income} = \text{GM} \div \text{TR} \times 100$$

$$\text{NPI in Naira} = \text{NPI} \div 100$$

(Breakdown in the appendix)

6.3 Factors that Constrain activities of Actors in the Value Chain

The varimax rotation method's factor analysis results of producers' limitations throughout the value chain of beef are displayed in Table 6.1. The data are suitable for factor analysis, as evidenced by the KMO index of 0.583 along with the Bartlett's sphere city of 0.000 (details in the appendix). Based on the item loadings and the limitations that producers in the value chain encountered, three criteria were identified from the data. These three elements were: financial, market/climatic, and social/infrastructural. Primary factors limiting the producers in the research region were the restrictions loaded under factor 1 and factor 2, then the constraints loaded under factors 3 and 4. The following particular constraints weighed particularly heavily on factor one: phony medications (.820), remoteness from drugstores (.790), intrusion of wild animals (-.545), and insufficient dipping system (.486). The biggest loading on factor one is found for counterfeit medications, suggesting that this is the main obstacle that producers of beef cattle in the research area must overcome. Lack of finance facilities (.697), disease prevalence (.606), lack of unions or cooperatives (.525), lack of extension contact (.376), and small capital (.352) were factors that weighted on factor three. Factor three's loading is largest when credit facilities are absent, suggesting that producers in the study area have restricted access to credit facilities.

Table 6.1: Factor Analysis Outcomes of Production Activity Restraints

Constraints	Factor 1	Factor 2	Factor 3
Fake Drugs	.820*	-.055	.102
Far Distances to Drug Centres	.790*	.083	.058
Invasion of Wild Animal	-.545*	-.198	-.110
Inadequate Dipping System	.486*	-.273	.308***
Small Capital	-.399*	-.073	.352***
High cost of Drugs	-.337*	.749**	.113
Theft	-.073	.720**	-.158
Drought	.370*	.591**	-.115
Fluctuation in Demand	-.273	.532**	.225
Absence of Credit Facilities	-.068	-.261	.697***
Prevalence of Diseases	.213	.148	.606***
Absence of Union/Co-operatives	.001	.408**	.525***
Lack of Extension Contact	.088	.001	.376***

Source: Field Survey, 2019

Key

- * – loaded variables on factor 1
- ** – loaded variables on factor 2
- *** – loaded variables on factor 3

Rotation method: Varimax (loading at 0.30 and above) with Kaiser normalization. Factors 1 and 2 are social and/or market factors, Factor 3 is financial, and Factor 4 is environmental.

The varimax rotation technique factor analysis of marketers' restrictions in the research area's beef value chain is presented in Table 6.2. The sustainability of the data for factor analysis is demonstrated by the KMO index of 0.518 and the Bartlett's sphere city of 0.015 (details are provided in the appendix). Based on the item loadings as barriers encountered by marketers along the value chain, three criteria were identified from the data. These aspects were marketing, socioeconomic/social, and financial/infrastructural. The main issue limiting the marketers in the research region was the limits imposed under factor 1, which were followed by constraints loaded under factors 2 and 3. Poor sales (.723), price fluctuations (.698), a subpar transportation system (.614), a lack of expansion capital (-.563), and theft (.462) were among the specific restrictions that loaded on factor one. The research area's market has a limited number of buyers of live cattle, as shown by the highest loading on factor one for poor sales. Theft (.346), livestock loss during transit (-.815), and low cattle quality (.530) were factors that scored highly on factor two. Cattle losses during transit had the highest loading on factor two, suggesting that it is the main obstacle that merchants in the study area must overcome. Poor cattle quality (.368) and marketers' time consumption (.882) were factors that weighted on factor three. Given the limited quantity of live cattle in the research area, it may be inferred that the sale of beef cattle takes a significant amount of time.

Table 6.2: Findings from a Factor Analysis of Marketing Activities' Constraints

Constraints	Factor 1	Factor 2	Factor 3
Poor Sale	.723*	-.065	-.121
Price Fluctuation	.698*	-.182	-.183
Poor transportation System	.614*	.162	.361***
Absence of expansion Capital	-.563*	.371**	-.213
Theft	.462*	.346**	-0.99
Loss of Cattle in Transit	.177	-.815**	.068
Poor Cattle Quality	.065	.530**	.368***
Time Consumption of marketer	-1.24	-0.17	.882***

Source: Field Survey, 2019

Key

- * – variables loaded on factor 1
- ** – variables loaded on factor 2
- *** – variables loaded on factor 3

Rotation Method: Varimax with loading at 0.30 and higher using Kaiser Normalization S. Factors 1 and 2 are financial, marketing, and socioeconomic, respectively.

The Varimax rotation technique factor analysis results of processor limitations in the beef value chain are displayed in Table 6.3. The sustainability of the data for factor analysis is demonstrated by the KMO index of 0.563 and the Bartlett's sphere city of 0.000 (details are provided in the appendix). Based on the item loadings as restrictions experienced by processors in the value chain, three components were extracted from the results. These included the following: social, processing, financial, and infrastructure factors. The primary restrictions facing the producers in the research region were those placed under factor 1, which were followed by constraints loaded under factors 2 and 3. The following specific constraints placed on factor one: high service charges (.660), high transportation costs (.538), poor storage facilities (-.482), and levies on abattoir operations (.750).The research area's processors are mostly constrained by levies on abattoir operations, as indicated by the largest loading on factor one. Customers' preferences (.718), a shoddy power supply (.607), and demand fluctuations (.579) were factors that weighed highly on factor two. Consumer preference has the largest loading on component two, suggesting that customers in the research area have a preference for buying fresh meat. Low operational mechanization (.757) and low-quality meat (-.457) were constraints that put a burden on factor three. The processors with the least amount of mechanization in their operations had the highest loading on factor three, suggesting that they have limited access to machinery for simple processing.

Table 6.3 : Factor Analysis Results of Constraints in processing Activities

Constraints	Factor 1	Factor 2	Factor 3
Levies on Abattoirs Operations	.750*	.277	.086
High Service Charge	.660*	-.068	.480***
High cost of Transportation	.538*	-.215	-.662
Absences of Storage Facilities	.495*	-.376	-.662
Consumers Preference	-0.27	.718**	-.036
Poor Power Supply	-.231	.607**	.036
Demand Fluctuation	.091	.579**	-.043
Minimal Mechanization in Operation	-0.91	-0.68	-.757***
Poor Beef Quality	-0.26	0.86	-.457***

Source: Field survey, 2019

Key

* – variables loaded on factor 1

** – variables loaded on factor 2

*** – variables loaded on factor 3

Rotation method: Kaiser normalization applied to Varimax (loading at 0.40 and above). Affordability and infrastructure make up component 1, social factors make up factor 2, and processing makes up factor 3.

7. CONCLUSION

The bulk of the players in the study region were men, most of them were married, and most of them lacked a formal education, according to the study's findings. The bulk of responders were, predictably, migrants. The Value chain for beef revealed activities of the major actors in the beef value chain which showed high intensity of value addition and complex interaction among the actors and it has helped to open new market opportunities for producers, marketers and processors by increasing their economic return, increase job creation down the value chain which in turn reduces poverty in the study area. Hence there the unemployed youth would easily and quickly fit into the beef industry. The use of extensive system of production and open housing system was high and the breed majorly reared was White Fulani. Beef cattle were majorly sold through terminal markets via cash. Small scale of processing was also paramount and Contact with consumers was direct along the value chain. The production, processing and marketing enterprises were profitable because they are all giving a positive return. The high profit enjoyed by the marketers was traced back to the role of the middlemen in the beef industry.

Finally, it was concluded that infrastructural/social factors (fake drugs, far distance to drug centres, invasion of wild animals and in adequate dipping system) were the major factors constraining the producers. Also, financial/ infrastructural factors (levies on abattoir operation, high service charge, high cost of transportation, poor storage facilities) were also the major factors constraining the processors. While the main obstacles experienced by the marketers in the research area were financial and infrastructure-related (poor sales, price fluctuations, bad transportation system, lack of expansion capital, and theft).

8. RECOMMENDATION

The study's conclusions lead to the following suggestions for strengthening Kogi state's sustainable beef value chain:

- Governmental organizations, the banking and microfinance industries, and specific credit and guarantee programs are needed to lessen credit access challenges along the value chain.
- The federal government in conjunction with state and local governments should construct and establish a deep-in-system at strategic places where cattle rearers (especially nomadic) can access control and maintenance of livestock productivity.
- For convenient beef transportation, mobile cool rooms should be made available by the government and neighborhood-based organizations. This would improve quality and lessen the limitations caused by the high perishability of beef.
- The result of the findings shows that actors lack extension contact. Hence, there is a need for the establishment of information in the area by the local and state government for those in the beef industry especially the producers to have access to extension workshop schemes in a form that would be easily comprehended taking into cognizance that they had no formal education.
- To lessen the problem of theft, the local, state, federal, and even security agencies should make an effort to grant cattle owners and marketers a special pass.

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